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Assessment of the effects of Fenton's oxidative treatment on the physicochemical properties of 10% simulated kerosene and gasoline contaminated surface water of the Ogbe Ijoh River, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Surface water taken from the Ogbe Ijoh River was simulated to 10% contaminations with kerosene and gasoline fractions of petroleum. Fenton oxidation treatment was then applied to remediate the polluted water in order to remove total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) as kerosene and gasoline. The physicochemical properties of the initial surface water, and after contaminations, as well as after remediation were analysed using standard methods. Comparison of these values shows that most of the properties were negatively impacted by simulated contaminations. Marked quality improvement compared to the contaminated water was observed for the remediated water particularly with regards to the: turbidity, total dissolved solid (TDS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), and total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) content. However, the pH, phosphates, total alkalinity, electrical conductivity, and metals content (Cd, Ni, & Pb) remains negatively impacted even after treatment; and therefore may require further treatment before use or discharge to receiving water bodies.

Keywords: Remediation, total petroleum hydrocarbons, Ogbe Ijoh River, Fenton's reagent, contamination

1. INTRODUCTION

Surface water, particularly river water furnishes valuable resources which include the protection and propagation of aquatic lives (e.g. fishes), recreation, irrigation and public water supply etc. (Chokor, 2021a). Thus, their contaminations represent danger to man and the ecosystem. The presence of petroleum hydrocarbons pollutants in river water is recognized to cause imbalance in the aquatic ecosystem and has contributed to the manifestations of some irregularities in physiology of aquatic species and their predators as they tend to concentrate and / or bio-accumulate some of these hydrocarbons in their body tissues (Enuneku et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2015; Chokor, 2021b; Giddings, 1981; Yang, 2007; Pham, 2010).

The effects of petroleum hydrocarbon exposure to organisms and human health have been variously described by various authors to include: the disruption in the activities of various body organs (such as: the pancreas, kidney, liver, blood circulatory system) and ultimately death; humans health complications (like skin irritation and rashes, genotoxicity, respiratory system disorders, cancers of different parts of the body, deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) damage, birth defects, childhood leukaemia, infertility and miscarriages in women) (Oyinbo et al., 2018; Ite et al., 2018; Coleman et al., 1984; Covinich et al., 2018).

The need therefore for hydrocarbon-contaminated water, to be remediated can never be overemphasized. Remediation involves the removal of contaminant(s) or rendering it into harmless form. Just as contaminations alter the physicochemical characteristics of the water bodies, so also does the treatment process alter the original physicochemical property of the water being treated; and the overall quality of the water may be affected negatively or positively depending on the treatment processes.

Fenton oxidative treatment of water is one of the promising techniques for the destructions of organic pollutants from water and waste water. The method involves in situ generation of hydroxyl radicals (OH^*) by the reaction of Fe^{2+} and H_2O_2 for the oxidation of pollutants into harmless products (e.g. CO_2 & H_2O); and offers the advantages of: being operational at ambient temperature, environmentally friendly, and short reaction time (few hours) of completion (Covinich et al., 2018).

Though, some works have been carried out on the physicochemical properties of the Ogbe Ijoh River, they were majorly from grab samples, in this work we focus on 20 hours composite samples taken from various sites and aggregated to form one composited sample. This is to ensure that the average properties of the river over time are revealed. Also because the Niger-Delta which the River is located is prone to occasional oil spills, we have decided to simulate contamination with 10% kerosene and gasoline in the assessment processes. In this work, we examined the physicochemical characteristics of surface water from the Ogbe Ijoh River and compared it to its simulated 10% kerosene and gasoline contaminated one, as well as one treated with Fenton's reagents.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study area

The Ogbe Ijoh River is situated in Warri south west of Delta state Nigeria (N 05°28'40.1" to N 05°29'02.2" and E 05°44'10.4" to E 05°44'14.0"); and is one of the distributaries of the Warri River which joins and enters the Forcados River before emptying into the Atlantic

ocean. The coast land – Ogbe Ijoh – is a low-lying land with mean height of about 5 m above sea levels and a gradient which decreases towards the river. The people’s occupation was until recently principally fishing, water transportations and sand dredging. However, recent times have seen the bank being characterized with increasing industrial activities which has given birth to increased pollution level.

Fig. 1. Map showing Ogbe Ijoh River and the sampled area.

2. 2. Sample collection, preparation and analysis

Composite sampling were carried out by collecting water samples from the surface of the river at two hourly intervals for over 20 hours period and the flow rate being measured each time interval of collections. Thereafter, a single composite sampling was made by mixing the 10 separate two-hourly samples from the various stations (Fig. 1), using volumes proportional to the flow rate at the time of sampling. The samples were put in pre-cleaned 250 ml capacity amber glass bottles with aluminium-lined screw cap and kept in ice chest at temperature below 4°C for onward transportation to the laboratory. In the laboratory, a portion of the samples were analysed for physicochemical properties using standard methods as described by Ademoriti (1996), and Chokor (2021a,c). The other portions were contaminated with 10 percent volumes of kerosene and also of gasoline and thoroughly mixed by the use of a mechanical shaker to produced 10% contaminations. These were then remediated with Fenton’s reagents. The physicochemical properties after contaminations, and remediation were again determined using same standard methods. The Petroleum Refinery Company (PRC) Warri, Delta State, Nigeria was the source the hydrocarbons viz; domestic purpose kerosene (DPK) and automotive gasoline used for the simulation of contaminations in this study.

2. 3. Fenton's Treatment

This was carried out by using the optimum quantities of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and iron II sulphate (Fe_2SO_4) [22,500 mg (22.5g) H_2O_2 and 200 mg $FeSO_4$ per L of 10% contaminated water treatment] as determined in optimization experiment (Fallah et al., 2015; Mohammad et al., 2016).

2. 4. Quality control and assurance

In order to ensure the accuracy and reliability of results obtained, analytical grade reagents (BDH and Sigma) were used. All glasses and plastics were cleansed by acid and rinsed with distilled water. Scientific standard solutions were used for calibrations. Blank determinations were subjected to similar extraction methods using same reagents. The analyses were carried out in triplicates and the results are expressed as mean and standard deviation from the mean (\pm).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows some of the physicochemical properties, metals levels and Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPHs) contents of the Ogbe Ijoh River surface water; before and after simulations with 10% kerosene and gasoline contaminations; as well as after treatment with Fenton's reagent; in comparison with the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ, 2015) and the World Health Organization guidelines for drinking water quality (WHO, 2017).

The mean pH of the surface water was 6.90 ± 0.02 , which was in conformity to the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality range of 6.5 – 8.5.

After contaminations the pH fell to 5.93 and 6.60 for the kerosene and gasoline contaminated water respectively. Kerosene and gasoline though not inherently acidic, contain organic substances that react with water to yield acidic by-products that help to lower the water's pH.

The pH of the treated water was 10.50 and 10.70 for kerosene and gasoline contaminated water respectively. The use of NaOH solution to stop the continuous production of hydroxyl radicals (*OH) and bring the reaction to an end is responsible for the rise in pH.

The turbidity value in Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU) of the surface water (48.27) rose drastically to 561.8 and 588.6 after contaminations with 10% kerosene and gasoline respectively; but came down to 14.17 and 12.24 after treatment. The Dissolved Oxygen (DO) value of 7.20 mg/L recorded for the surface water was sufficient for aquatic lives to prevent oxygen deficiency.

This decreased to 4.10 and 3.40 mg/L after contaminations with 10% kerosene and gasoline respectively. The presence of oil reduces free diffusion of air (oxygen) into the water hence this reduction in DO. However, after treatment, there was improvement in DO value to 5.70 and 6.20 mg/L with respect to kerosene and gasoline contaminated waters. The DO could not be restored to its initial value because the oil before removal could have killed some algae that release oxygen into the water. The Fenton's reagent could also have resulted same effects.

These values for the remediated waters however, satisfy the minimum requirement for aquatic life to prevent oxygen deficiency.

Table 1. Some physicochemical properties and metals contents of the Ogbe Ijoh surface water, after contaminations with 10% kerosene and gasoline and treatments with Fenton’s reagent.

Parameters	Surface water.	Contaminated water		Remediated water		Standards
		10% Kerosene	10% Gasoline	10% Kerosene	10% Gasoline	
pH	6.90±0.02	5.93±0.15	6.60±0.30	10.50±0.06	10.70±0.05	6.5 - 8.5 ^a
Turbidity (NTU)	48.27±0.15	561.8±0.49	588.60±0.50	14.17±0.12	12.24±0.15	5 ^a
DO (mg/L)	7.20±1.03	4.10±0.45	3.40±0.27	5.70±0.10	6.20±0.17	
BODs (mg/L)	4.65±0.15	6.50±0.21	7.40±0.20	5.80±0.06	7.80±1.15	
CODs (mg/L)	17.27±0.00	27.00±0.2	31.50±0.22	6.70±0.10	7.50±0.25	
TPHs (mg/L)	0.437±0.07	4820.4±3.40	5208.4±4.50	438.6±3.50	306.7±5.10	0.3
TDS (mg/L)	62.54±1.53	104.00±0.27	106.10±0.35	20.35±0.06	22.60±0.25	500 ^a
TSS (mg/L)	1.56±0.04	1.70±0.30	1.71±0.36	1.60±0.10	1.64±0.14	
Cl (mg/L)	117.25±0.0	142.26±0.33	182.30±0.34	142.20±0.34	120.30±0.19	250 ^a
Cond.(µs/cm)	163.10±0.10	147.30±0.40	133.00±0.50	956.17±0.12	1045.10±0.55	1000 ^a
Phosphates	0.38±0.11	0.53±0.02	0.52±0.08	0.66±0.03	0.68±0.04	
NH ₃ (mg/L)	0.67±0.01	0.33±0.01	0.26±0.02	0.08±0.01	0.04±0.02	
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	6.00±0.28	11.00±0.27	15.50±0.30	8.00±0.16	8.00±0.15	50 ^{ab}
T. Alkalinity (mg/LCaCO ₃)	118.67±0.15	102.5±0.71	116.48±1.24	21.64±4.00	23.20±1.30	30 - 500
Cd (mg/L)	0.13±0.001	0.13±0.01	0.14±0.03	0.11±0.01	0.13±0.01	0.003 ^{ab}
Cr (mg/L)	0.09±0.01	0.11±0.01	0.13±0.01	0.11±0.01	0.13±0.01	0.05 ^{ab}
Ni (mg/L)	0.31±0.01	0.39±0.01	0.44±0.02	0.04±0.02	0.30±0.01	0.02 ^a
Pb (mg/L)	0.07±0.01	0.09±0.01	0.14±0.02	0.09±0.01	0.04±0.03	0.01 ^{ab}
V (mg/L)	0.01±0.01	0.02±0.01	0.04±0.02	0.01±0.00	0.03±0.01	

a = Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ), b = World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines for drinking water quality

The five-day Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD₅) followed the inverse trend with DO. This is expected from their inverse relationship. The Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) increased largely after contaminations but decreased even to a lower value after treatment. The COD/BOD ratio was much lower in treated water compared to the simulated contaminated water. This signifies efficiency of the treatment process.

Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPHs) was relatively low (0.437 mg/L) before contaminations. This increased after contaminations with 10% kerosene and gasoline, to 4820.4 and 5208.4 mg/L respectively. The values of the treated waters were 438.6 and 306.7 mg/L respectively for the kerosene and gasoline contaminated waters representing 90.90 and 94.11% reduction in TPHs respectively. This evidenced the ability of the Fenton's oxidative process towards removal of hydrocarbons contaminations from the water. Total Dissolved Solid (TDS) rose very high after contaminations. This could be as a result of the oil bringing into solution organic matter suspended in the water. The value reduces after remediation treatment as the removal of the oil is accompanied with the removal of some dissolved salts of metals and organic. There was no marked increase in Total Suspended Solid (TSS) throughout the process; as contaminations did results to significant change in TSS, neither did treatment process either.

The chlorides (Cl^-) content increased slightly from 117.25 to 142.26 and 182.30 mg/L for kerosene and gasoline contaminated waters. After treatment, the value remains high; 142.20 mg/L for kerosene and 120.30 mg/L for gasoline contaminated water. The values were however, still within the maximum permissible limit of 250 mg/L.

There was reduction in electrical conductivity from 163.10 to 147.36 and 133.0 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$ for 10% kerosene and gasoline contaminations respectively. The retardation of ionic movement created by the non-polar environment induced by kerosene and gasoline resulted to reduction in electrical conductivity in the contaminated waters (Fakunle et al., 2021). The marked increase in conductivity (956.17 and 1045.10 for kerosene and gasoline contaminated water) after remediation could be adduced to two reasons. First, is due to increase ions in solution resulting from the ions/salt contain in the Fenton's reagent itself. Secondly, the increased mobility of the ions in solution arising from more polar environment created by the removal of hydrocarbons fractions of the kerosene and gasoline. Thus, the increased conductivity is an indicator of high remediation efficiency. Phosphates (PO_4^{3-}) and ammonia (NH_3) increased in value all through the process. Nitrates (NO_3^-) increase after contaminations but decreases after treatment. The values for nitrates concentrations throughout the process were within the recommended value (Table 1).

The alkalinity – the acid neutralizing capacity – of both the surface and simulated contaminated surface water were within the recommended range (30 – 500 mg/L CaCO_3). However, the water samples treated by Fenton's reagent fell below the standard range. The low value obtained for the treated samples is likely due to the oxidative nature of the treatment process in which the highly reactive Fenton' reagent (H_2O_2 & FeSO_4) decomposes the carbonates present in water samples to CO_2 and H_2O (Covinich et al., 2018). The low alkalinity of the treated water means that the water's pH could easily drops much below 7 when contaminated with acidic solutions. This may hinder the reproductive capacity of aquatic lives and even cause death

After 10% contamination with kerosene; cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), and vanadium (V) content in the water rose in value. This may have resulted from the presence of these metals in this petroleum fraction. There were decrease in most metals content particularly Ni after treatment. Chromium (Cr) and lead (Pb) however, did not show any significant decrease. Some of these metals must have been trapped in the iron hydroxide [$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$] which was formed and separated as slag during the process. With exception of Cr and Pb, the values of metals contents in the remediated waters were lower than that of the original surface water. The values were however (with exception of V) still higher than the standard established by the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ, 2015).

The gasoline contaminated water showed similar increase in metal contents for all metals. These values also decrease for all metals after remediation with the Fenton's reagent (Table 1).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The examinations of physicochemical properties of the Ogbe Ijoh River Water shows that most of the properties were largely within the stipulated standard established by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ). However, the turbidity, and metals' content of Cd, Cr, and Pb were higher than the recommended standard. Contaminations with 10% kerosene and gasoline impacted most physicochemical properties negatively. The pH becomes more acidic, turbidity increased drastically, dissolved oxygen (DO) decreased, while, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) increase as the total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) rose from 0.437 to 4820.4 and 5208.4 mg/L for kerosene and gasoline contaminated water respectively. Slight increases were also noted for metals content after contaminations.

Treatment of the contaminated water with Fenton's reagent however, impacted most of the water characteristics positively but left some such as the: pH, total alkalinity, conductivity, and metals content with much to be desired. Hence the needs for further treatment before reuse or discharge into nearby aquifers.

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